

from triphenylsilyllithium and decaphenylcyclopentasilane) with 1, 6-dichlorododecamethylhexasilane in THF.

The structures of the above three linear polysilanes were assigned by analytical and spectral evidences. Little quantity of hexaphenyldisilane was formed during the preparation of each of the polysilanes (I-III). This is supported by the previous study of halogen-metal interconversion reaction of phenylsilyllithium compounds with mono and polyhaloalkanes⁸.

Experimental

The dodecamethylcyclohexasilane was prepared by the interaction of lithium and dichlorodimethylsilane in THF. 1, 4 and 1, 6-dichloropolysilanes were prepared by the chlorine cleavage of dodecamethylcyclohexasilane in carbon tetrachloride. All reactions were carried out with oven dried glassware in an atmosphere of dry oxygen-free nitrogen. Melting points were recorded in Mel-Temp apparatus. (All experimental work done in the Chemical Laboratory, Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa U.S.A.)

General procedure for the preparation of polysilanes (I-III)

To 0.01 mole of α, ω -dihalopolysilane in 50 ml of THF, 0.02 mole of silyllithium compound in THF was added dropwise with stirring. The Gilman Colour Test⁹ was negative immediately after the addition was complete. The reaction mixture was hydrolysed with water and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined organic layers were dried with sodium sulphate, concentrated and cooled when hexaphenyldisilane was separated and identified through mixed melting point with an authentic sample. It was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation left a residue which was chromatographed over alumina. Petrol ether (60-80°) eluted polysilane compound. Analytical sample was prepared by repeated crystallisation from suitable solvent (vide Table I).

TABLE—I

Polysilanes	Yield %	M.P. °C	Solvent for cryst.	Analysis ^a		
				C	H	Si
I	50	182	Petrol ether (60-80°)	70.91 (70.34)	7.24 (7.19)	22.92 (22.45)
II	54	156	"	66.51 (66.45)	7.99 (7.6)	25.71 (25.9)
III	45	222	Cyclohexane	69.97 (70.2)	7.04 (6.9)	22.76 (22.56)

^a. Figure in the parenthesis shows the calculated value.

The pattern of the IR. spectra of the polysilanes (I-III) are comparable, showing peaks around 7.8-8.0 μ due to Si-Me and 6.9, 8.9 and 13.5-14.4 μ due to Si-Ph groups. No bands due to Si-O-Si and Si-OH groups were noted. The PMR analysis of the three polysilanes gave the ratios of aliphatic to aromatic protons in good agreement with the theoretical values.

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